

Development High-Strength Medium Manganese Steels for Automotive Industry

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Abstract: New medium manganese steels for automotive industry, to satisfy challenging performance requirements for high-energy absorption (total elongation (A_{50}) $\geq 18\%$, ultimate tensile strength (R_m) ≥ 1200 MPa) and anti-intrusion (A_{50} $\geq 10\%$, R_m ≥ 1500 MPa) parts, were designed and investigated by using a series of characterization techniques. An alloy design strategy involving thermodynamic modeling to determine critical transformation temperatures (A_{e1} , A_{e3} , M_s) and to predict phase transformation behaviour (volume fraction and chemistry of phases) was adopted. Nine alloy were designed, manufactured and subjected to industrial simulations of the hot dip galvanizing and hot pressing by means of dilatometry and then subjected to mechanical testing. Finally, the alloys satisfying the mechanical properties were subjected to microstructural characterization. The resulting materials exhibited microstructures consisting of ferrite, reverted stable austenite and martensite, with hardness values in the range of 400–500 HV, ultimate tensile strengths between 1200 and 1700 MPa, and total elongation of 10–22%.

Key words: Medium Manganese Steels, Austenite Reversion, Intercritical Annealing, Alloy Design.

Introduction

Medium manganese steels (MMnS), containing 3–12 wt.% Mn, have emerged as promising materials within the class of third-generation advanced high-strength steels (3G-AHSS). The microstructure consists of retained austenite ($\gamma > 10$ vol.%) embedded in a ferritic (α) and/or martensitic (α') matrix^[1]. Owing to the versatility of their heat treatment routes, these steels can achieve a wide range of mechanical properties, with ultimate tensile strengths in the range 800-1500 MPa and total elongation values between 10% and 45%. Moreover, the presence of manganese effectively reduces the ferrite-to-austenite (γ) transformation temperatures (A_{e1} and A_{e3}), allowing for lower reheating and hot forming temperatures. This makes them suitable for "warm stamping" (WS) applications^[2–5]. This project aimed at developing MMnS with enhanced energy absorption capacity and high resistance to intrusion.

1. Alloy design

1.1. Mechanical and technological property requirements

The objective of the investigation was to develop medium manganese steels able to fulfil the following mechanical and technological requirements: i) Intrusion Resistance ($R_m \geq 1500$ MPa and $A_{50} \geq 10\%$) after stamping, ii) Energy Absorption Capacity ($R_m \geq 1200$ MPa and $A_{50} \geq 18\%$, $R_m \times A_{50} \geq 21$ GPa.%), iii) Absence of liquid metal embrittlement (LME) even in presence of zinc coating.

1.2. Criteria and priorities for the alloy design

During the alloy design the following priorities were established to achieve the mentioned requirements:

- 1) Use of common & relatively cheap alloying elements (C, Mn, Si, Cr, Al);
- 2) Low A_{e3} to minimize the reheating temperature during stamping;
- 3) Mn (<5 wt.%) to avoid difficulties in steelmaking and casting;
- 4) Si (<1 wt.%) to inhibit cementite precipitation, provide solid solution strengthening and prevent zinc coating defects;
- 5) Al (<1 wt.%) and Cr (<0.25 wt.%) to widen the (A_{e3} - A_{e1}) range for adequate phase-balance, avoid sticking during casting, and environmental reason;
- 6) Ti, Nb, V microalloying for grain refinement and precipitation strengthening, and B (~0.0025 wt.%) to improve dynamic mechanical properties.

1.3. Alloy design methodology

After the selection of the alloying elements the alloys design proceeded with thermodynamic calculations, involving: i) the evaluation of the equilibrium phase fractions as a function of the temperature (α , γ), ii) prediction of transformation temperatures (A_{e1} , A_{e3}), iii) M_s calculation using the equation proposed by Imai et al. ($M_s = 539 - 423C - 30.4Mn - 7.5Si + 30Al$ ^[6]) taking the intercritical FCC chemistry from the ThermoCalc predictions, iv) calculation of the final austenite content at room temperature using Koistinen-Marburger formula

($V_M = 1 - \exp[-0.011 * (M_S - T)^n]$) to deduce global phase fractions at room temperature.

2. Alloy preparation and heat treatment and characterization

After the design of alloys using the above methodology, 9 variants were selected. The alloys were fabricated in form of 25 kg ingots and subjected to hot cold and cold rolling. Then fabricated alloys were subjected to a double intercritical annealing treatment. First intercritical annealing included heating in the range 700-760 °C for 1 min, rapid cooling to 470 °C (1 min) for the simulation of the galvanizing process followed by cooling to room temperature. The second annealing included reheating at 700 °C and 750 °C for 3 minutes to room temperature to simulate the typical hot stamping route. The variant fulfilling the requirements in 1.1 were the ones selected for microstructural characterization using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and Vickers hardness measurement.

3. Results

The alloys that satisfied the mechanical property requirements have compositions as given in Table 1.

Table 1 Chemical composition of the developed alloy

C	Mn	Al	Si	Cr	Ti+ Nb+ V
<0.23	<5	<1.0	0.25	0.25	0.2

The microstructure consists of mixture of ferrite, martensite and fresh martensite as illustrated in **Figure 1**, with volume fractions of phases listed in **Table 2**. The mechanical properties that can be derived from the engineering stress-strain curves in **Figure 1**, demonstrate that the high temperature intercritical annealing (750 °C) leads to satisfy high anti-intrusion requirement, while low temperature intercritical annealing (700 °C) allows to meet the requirement for energy absorbing parts. The high temperature intercritical annealing led to higher fractions of martensite while the lower temperature annealing resulted in more retained austenite to account for the transformation induced plasticity (TRIP) effect.

Figure 1 (a) Medium manganese steel microstructure (b) Tensile curves. (1) and (2) represent the mechanical property targets. (α : Ferrite, α' : Martensite, γ : Austenite)

Table 2 Phase volume fractions determined through XRD measurements

α (vol. %)	α' (vol. %)	γ (vol. %)	$C\gamma$ (wt. %)
31-75	16-77	5-37	0.2-0.4

4. Conclusions

- Warm Stamping MMnS were designed using phase transformation theory and modelling approach, considering industrial processing requirements.
- The experimental steels achieved requirements for the energy absorbing parts ($R_m > 1200$ MPa) with good total elongation ($A_{50} > 18\%$), and anti-intrusion part ($R_m > 1500$ MPa and elongation $A_{50} > 10\%$) due to high and optimized amounts of α/α' and γ .

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